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Tight belts, different cuts: How political preferences shape the effects of fiscal rules

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Abstract

While fiscal rules are often viewed as an effective way to curb the deficit bias arising from, inter alia, partisan pressures in common-pool budget settings, much less is known about how their effects vary with partisan preferences. This paper fills that gap by estimating local projections for a panel of EU-27 countries over 1995–2019. We innovatively link COFOG expenditure categories with the Manifesto Project Database to study how political preferences condition the impact of tighter fiscal rules across spending functions. Our first result is that more stringent national fiscal rules are associated with lower public spending in the short- and medium-run. Digging deeper, we show that the recomposition of expenditure under tighter rules depends on governments' preferences: adjustment falls disproportionately on categories that are less favoured by the incumbent. These results are robust to alternative estimators, different definitions of the dependent variable, and placebo tests. Lastly, the cuts associated with stricter fiscal rules in low-preference government contexts are amplified when sovereign debt yields are higher.

Keywords: • Fiscal rules • Public spending composition • Local projections • COFOG

JEL Classification: • E62 • P48 • D78 • H87

1 Introduction

Despite the recent reform of the EU fiscal framework, voices have already been raised claiming that the fiscal rules may themselves be in need of reform.¹ The arguments for such a precocious reform essentially relate to the current need to increase spending in specific domains that are considered long neglected. While the current debate often refers to the exclusion of defence spending, proposals made prior to the reform also advocated excluding green investment, in the form of a “green golden rule”.² More recently, a related line of thinking has emphasised the need to scale up the provision of European public goods in order to support shared objectives, including defence, climate policy and strategic autonomy.³

While the current debate suggests that some of these spending categories should be excluded because of underspending on these priorities due to pressures to meet fiscal targets, it is not yet clear in the literature how fiscal rules, and more specifically stringent ones, shape the functional composition of public spending. While some authors have investigated the impact of fiscal rules on the decomposition of investment versus consumption spending, fewer have taken into account functional decomposition [Barnes et al., 2023]. In that respect, this paper takes one step further, as it not only studies the effect of stringent fiscal rules on the recomposition of government spending, but also highlights one important transmission channel, namely the political preferences of governments in power.

We innovatively match the Classification of the Functions of Government (CO-

¹Pench, L. (2025, July 15). European Union fiscal rules: it’s already time to reform the reform. *Bruegel analysis*. <https://www.bruegel.org/analysis/european-union-fiscal-rules-its-already-time-reform-reform>

²DG Trésor. (2022, February 28). European fiscal rules in the air. *Direction générale du Trésor*. <https://www.tresor.economie.gouv.fr/Articles/2022/02/28/european-fiscal-rules-in-the-air>

³Zettelmeyer, J. (2024, October 29). European public goods: time for action now. *Bruegel analysis*. <https://www.bruegel.org/analysis/european-public-goods-time-action-now>

FOG) with the Manifesto Project Database (MPD) to address these research questions. While COFOG allows for a breakdown of government spending by function (defence, education, environmental protection, ...), the MPD uses textual analysis of parties' election manifestos to derive their preferences across several policy areas. Merging these datasets helps us capture how fiscal rule enforcement affects spending across functions, conditional on the preferences of the parties in government. The data cover the EU-27 over the period 1995–2019. We find that more stringent rules are associated with lower government spending as a share of GDP, but that this reduction is unevenly distributed across functions. After conditioning on governing parties' preferences, the tightening of fiscal rules disproportionately affects spending categories that are less favoured by the incumbent.

Thus, while stronger fiscal rules are effective in reducing spending, their effects are not independent of political preferences: less prioritised categories bear a larger share of the adjustment. These results are robust to alternative estimators, alternative measures of the dependent variable, and placebo tests. As an additional source of heterogeneity, stricter rules lead to an exacerbated recomposition of spending when political preferences are combined with a tight fiscal position, as reflected in high government bond yields.

These results provide a timely contribution to the current debate, as they stress the importance of governments' political considerations in the compositional effects of fiscal rules on spending. While excluding some priority spending items from the rules may appear to some as a solution, our results also suggest that successive governments with different preferences may naturally lead to inconsistent priorities, underscoring the need for long-term frameworks that could foster inter-partisan cooperation. In addition to highlighting further challenges for the current numerical fiscal rules—perhaps too simple for an overly complex issue, as suggested by [Blanchard et al. \[2021\]](#)—in an

era of rising populism and tighter fiscal conditions, we also extend the discussion to potential mitigating solutions and good institutional practices that may help reconcile fiscal discipline with shifting policy priorities.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature. Section 3 describes the data and key measures. Section 4 presents the main results. Section 5 reports robustness checks. Section 6 concludes with policy implications.

2 Related literature

This paper connects two strands of research—(i) how fiscal rules affect the level and composition of public expenditure, and (ii) how partisan preferences shape spending choices—and asks whether the compositional impact of fiscal rules is conditioned by governments’ preferences. Methodologically, we innovatively match COFOG spending functions to the Manifesto Project Database (MPD), allowing party priorities to enter directly into a function-level analysis of fiscal rule effects.

2.1 Fiscal rules, deficit bias, and the composition of spending

A large literature argues that fiscal rules curb the deficit bias rooted in common-pool problems and principal–agent frictions. Empirically, rule-based frameworks are often associated with lower deficits and slower spending growth, although effectiveness varies with institutional features such as inflation-targeting regimes (Combes et al. [2018]), the degree of budget transparency (Gootjes and De Haan [2022]), and the presence of independent fiscal institutions (Beetsma et al. [2019]; Căpraru et al. [2022]; or Guerguil et al. [2017] on the cyclicity of fiscal policy). In a recent contribution Apeti et al. [2025] also show that fiscal rules not only lead to lower spending but are also associated with higher efficiency of the government spending. Beyond

aggregate levels, a smaller but important strand of the literature studies composition, historically along economic categories (investment vs. current).

Early contributions show that constraints can interact with capital budgeting: [Poterba \[1995\]](#) documents that balanced-budget rules and capital budgets shape the split between investment and current spending. [Balassone and Franco \[2000\]](#) argue that SGP-type rules may bias against public investment, while warning that an EMU-level golden rule would face monitoring and opportunism issues. [Blanchard and Giavazzi \[2004\]](#) discuss the pros and cons of exempting investment, including reclassification risks. Subsequent empirical work is mixed: [Turrini \[2004\]](#) finds that investment fell in the immediate post-Maastricht period—especially in high-debt countries—but the effect later weakened as fiscal space improved; [Perée and Vålilä \[2005\]](#) find no systematic EMU impact on investment levels. Broadening beyond investment, [Dahan and Strawczynski \[2013\]](#) show that stronger rules reduce total spending growth and shift composition away from transfers relative to government consumption, with sharper effects where social rights are weakly protected. More recent evidence suggests consumption is compressed more than investment in many settings (e.g., [Venturis \[2023\]](#)).

Moving from economic to functional composition, EU spending patterns differ markedly across countries and enlargements [[Ferreiro et al., 2010](#)], and classification into “productive” vs. “unproductive” functions using COFOG is debated [[Ferreiro et al., 2009](#)], yet remains policy-relevant given guidance to tilt spending toward “productive” uses. At the sub-national level, [Venturini \[2020\]](#) shows that tighter local rules in Italy reallocated spending away from investment—especially human capital and infrastructure—when analysed through COFOG. Domain-specific concerns have also emerged: some contributions suggest that tight fiscal constraints may lower environmental debt in the longer run, but at the cost of reduced abatement spending

in the short run (Boly et al. [2022]); proposals for a “green golden rule” have been advanced (Darvas and Wolff [2021]), alongside warnings about green-washing.

The study closest to ours is Barnes et al. [2023], who document a recomposition of government spending across COFOG functions in response to fiscal rules in OECD countries. They also show substantial cross-country heterogeneity in how governments reallocate spending across functions.

Overall, the literature establishes that rules can alter composition, but evidence at the COFOG function level, and especially its potential drivers, is still limited.

2.2 Partisan preferences, manifesto priorities, and politics conditioning

Partisan theories posit systematic differences in macroeconomic and fiscal priorities. Hibbs [1977] emphasises left–right differences in the inflation–unemployment trade-off. In the fiscal domain, left governments are often associated with higher total spending (Blais et al. [1993]; Cusack [1997]) and greater social expenditure (Hicks and Swank [1992]; Jensen [2012]). However, empirical findings are mixed, with several studies reporting weak or null partisan effects at both aggregate and disaggregate levels (Garrett and Mitchell [2001]; Kittel and Obinger [2003]).

A key insight from this literature is that such mixed evidence may partly reflect measurement limitations. Coarse left–right indicators can mask issue-specific policy priorities. Using party manifestos, Bräuninger [2005] show that partisan effects emerge when political preferences are measured through topical emphases rather than a single ideological axis (see also Budge and Farlie 1983). This motivates the use of the MPD to capture function-relevant policy priorities directly. In the same vein, Dassonneville et al. [2025] argue that party responsiveness is increasingly multidimensional

and cannot be adequately represented by a single left–right scale.

Building on the idea that political preferences are better captured through topic-specific measures derived from party manifestos, this paper tests the following hypotheses:

HP1 — Stringent fiscal rules lead to changes in the composition of government spending.

HP2 — Political preferences emerge as a plausible conditioning factor in shaping the effect of stringent fiscal rules on the composition of government spending.

3 Data and descriptive facts

As stated above, the analysis covers the EU-27 over the period 1995–2019. Our objective is to assess whether tighter fiscal rules—capturing additional fiscal pressure—shape the composition of government spending, and whether this compositional effect depends on governing parties’ preferences. To proxy fiscal pressure, we use a strength (stringency) measure of fiscal rules rather than a simple adoption dummy: it is not only the presence of a rule that matters, but also how strongly it constrains policymakers.

3.1 Fiscal rule stringency

EU accession entails a commitment to the Maastricht criteria, which embed numerical fiscal constraints for all Member States. However, beyond this common supranational baseline, there is substantial cross-country heterogeneity in the way fiscal rules are transposed into national legislation and enforced in practice, leading to marked differences in their effective stringency. These supranational requirements are typically

transposed into national frameworks and complemented by country-specific arrangements. National fiscal rules can apply at multiple levels of government (general, central, regional, local, and social security), and their stringency can be measured along several dimensions, including legal basis, coverage, escape clauses, independent monitoring, enforcement mechanisms, and sanctioning provisions.⁴

Figure 1: Distribution of national fiscal rule stringency in the EU-27, 1995–2019. Each ridge represents the cross-country distribution in a given year. Green (orange) shading denotes more (less) stringent national fiscal rules.

In this paper, we use the European Commission (DG ECFIN) indicator of fiscal

⁴More precisely, the Fiscal Rule Strength Index (FRSI) captures key institutional features of fiscal rules along five dimensions: (i) the statutory/legal basis of the rule (ranging from political commitment to constitutional anchoring); (ii) the extent to which objectives are binding and difficult to revise; (iii) the strength of monitoring arrangements, including the independence of the monitoring body, the existence of real-time surveillance, oversight of correction procedures, and the involvement of independent institutions in macroeconomic or budgetary forecasting; (iv) the presence and automaticity of correction mechanisms in case of deviation from the rule; and (v) the rule’s resilience to shocks, including escape clauses, safety margins, cyclical adjustment provisions, and exclusions for items outside government control.

rule stringency, which aggregates information on rules at all levels of government into a comparable index across countries and over time.

Figure 1 shows a clear trend towards stronger national fiscal rules across EU countries from 1995 to 2019. The distribution shifts to the right over time, indicating broad-based tightening rather than changes concentrated in a few countries. This pattern helps mitigate—though it does not eliminate—concerns about self-selection, whereby only the best fiscal performers would strengthen their rules. Ending the sample in 2019 also avoids confounding this gradual tightening with the exceptional suspension of EU fiscal rules triggered by the Covid-19 pandemic.

3.2 Measuring political preferences using manifestos (MPD)

In our study, this measure essentially serves to distinguish two different states: one in which political preference for a given spending category is high, and another in which it is low. As in [Bräuninger \[2005\]](#), rather than relying on a coarse left–right score, we prefer to use topic-specific salience (positive versus negative mentions), which we later align with COFOG functions.

Therefore, we choose to use the Manifesto Project Database (MPD; [Lehmann et al. \[2024\]](#)). The MPD codes quasi-sentences in party programmes into a standardised set of policy categories. Measures of political preferences are then constructed by calculating the proportion of statements devoted to each category.

Following [Bräuninger \[2005\]](#), we also restrict our analysis of political preferences stated in party manifestos to parties in government. This approach is consistent with the objective of the paper, as fiscal rules may set the stage for a recomposition of public spending in favour of the preferences of actual decision-makers, rather than some aggregate national preference.

While this seems a reasonable approach, it is not necessarily an easy task given the structure of the MPD dataset. Restricting the analysis to governing parties requires merging the MPD dataset with another source of information, in this case the ParlGov database [Döring and Manow, 2024], which precisely traces which parties entered government in each country and year. While the ParlGov data contain a variable with the MPD party ID, this variable includes many missing values (20.6% of the observations in our MPD dataset are not mapped using the ID in ParlGov). Knowing that some important governing parties were not matched due to missing MPD IDs, we therefore relied on the following procedure.

Party names were standardised (lowercased, stripped of punctuation, and trimmed) and tokenised into sets of words. We then computed the *Jaccard similarity* between each governing party name and a set of potential matches from the Manifesto Project Database (restricted to the same country and year). The Jaccard coefficient is defined as:

$$J(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}, \quad (1)$$

where A and B are sets of words from each party name. Matches were retained when $J(A, B) \geq 0.4$, and for each governing party the match with the highest similarity score was selected.⁵ This approach reduces the share of MPD party observations that cannot be matched to ParlGov to under 10% (9.2%).

After restricting the MPD to governing parties, for categories with both positive and negative mentions we use their net balance (positive minus negative) per manifesto. To obtain a credible measure of partisan preferences by function c that reflects the actual influence of governing parties, we weight party-level net mentions by parliamentary seat shares obtained in the relevant election year t :

⁵We replicated this exercise using higher cut-off thresholds, but this did not significantly change the results of the analysis. Results using alternative cut-offs are available upon request.

$$\zeta_{it}^c = \sum_j (\text{Positive}_{jit}^c - \text{Negative}_{jit}^c) \times \text{SeatShare}_{jit}, \quad (2)$$

where i indexes countries, t election years, and j parties. To make the manifesto-based indicators comparable across categories and countries, we standardise them (z-scores) so that each variable reflects deviations from its mean in units of standard deviations: $Z_{it}^c = (\zeta_{it}^c - \mu_c) / \sigma_c$. This ensures that the measures capture the relative salience of a policy area. Between election years, ζ_{it}^c is held constant using a Last Observation Carried Forward (LOCF) approach. We believe this has the advantage of not relying on strong assumptions about the evolution of preferences over time (as would be the case with linear interpolation). Moreover, this feature is important for the credibility of the subsequent state-dependence analysis, as the state must be pre-determined with respect to the shock (Auerbach and Gorodnichenko [2012]; Ramey and Zubairy [2018]). Using manifestos drafted prior to election dates and applying LOCF to complete the data helps limit concerns about reverse causality arising from rules enforced after elections. Panel (a) of Figure 2 shows the distributions of political preferences across categories. All distributions appear right-skewed, indicating the presence of governments with particularly strong favourable preferences for each policy area.

3.3 COFOG classification and matching with MPD

The Classification of the Functions of Government (COFOG) allocates public expenditure to functions at several levels of detail. We work at the COFOG I level, which groups total spending into ten broad functions that are consistently available across countries and over time. The MPD dataset codes party manifestos issued for national legislative elections. These elections determine the partisan composition of

the national legislature and shape the political environment in which central government fiscal policy is designed and implemented. It is therefore natural to restrict the COFOG data to the central government level in order to map political preferences to the spending categories over which governments have direct control.

As mentioned above, we use fiscal rules defined at all levels of government. While this does not perfectly align with the other two measures, we do not restrict this indicator to the central government level only, as most fiscal rules are binding at the general government level, thereby de facto including the central government. We therefore retain this measure and consider that the inclusion of other levels of government primarily introduces additional noise into the analysis.

Figure 2: Distributions of political preferences and central government spending by function. Panel (a) shows the distribution of the standardised indicator of government political preferences by COFOG category (Z_{it}^c), constructed from governing parties' election manifestos. Panel (b) displays the distribution of central government spending by COFOG category as a percentage of GDP. Each ridge represents the distribution across EU countries and years. Green (orange) shading denotes higher (lower) values. (wel: Welfare state; rec: Recreation, culture and religion; ord: Public order and safety; gen: General public services; env: Environmental protection; edu: Education; def: Defence)

Panel (b) of Figure 2 shows substantial variation across COFOG spending categories. It is therefore not surprising that welfare and general public services average 9.3% and 9.7%, respectively, considerably higher than the other categories. By comparison, recreation, environmental protection, public order, and defence together average 3.8%. Nevertheless, it is important to note that, while welfare and public services appear to be prioritised on average, the distribution is highly heterogeneous across the sample, with values ranging from 1.4% to 20.3% for welfare and from 2.5% to 23.0% for general public services.

As mentioned above, this paper matches the COFOG classification with the Manifesto Project Database (MPD) to study the compositional effects of fiscal rules conditional on political preferences. To this end, Table 1 reports the crosswalk between COFOG divisions and MPD categories. For MPD categories that record both positive and negative mentions, we take their net balance. For the category “Governmental and Administrative Efficiency”, positive mentions may imply lower administrative spending; we therefore multiply this measure by -1 so that higher values are a proxy for greater support for spending in the corresponding COFOG function.

It is worth mentioning that a known source of noise in COFOG is that Division *General public services* contains public debt transactions (interest payments). We also exclude COFOG Division *Economic affairs*, as it does not map cleanly into MPD categories and is likely to reflect a diffuse mix of manifesto themes, limiting interpretability.

Table 1: Matching COFOG divisions to MPD categories

(C) COFOG	Manifesto Project Database categories
(1) General public services	Governmental and Administrative Efficiency: Need for efficiency and economy in government and administration and/or the general appeal to make the process of government cheaper and more efficient. (Positive)*
(2) Defence	Military: The importance of external security and defence. (Positive / Negative)
(3) Public order and safety	Law and Order: Favourable mentions of strict law enforcement and tougher action against domestic crime. (Positive)
(4) Env. protection	Env. protection: Policies in favour of protecting the environment, fighting climate change, and other “green” policies. (Positive)
(5) Recreation, culture and religion	Culture: Need for state funding of cultural and leisure facilities including arts and sport. (Positive)
(6) Education	Education: Need to expand and/or improve educational provision at all levels. (Positive / Negative)
(7) Housing and community amenities Health Social protection	Welfare State: Mentions of introducing, maintaining, or expanding public social services or social security schemes. (Positive / Negative)

* Multiplied by -1 so that higher values indicate greater support for spending, improving comparability across functions.

4 Main results

4.1 Unconditional effects of fiscal rules

As mentioned earlier, this paper aims to assess the effect of fiscal rule reinforcements on the composition of government spending over the short and medium run. To this end, we adopt a local projection methodology *à la* Jordà [2005]. More specifically, we follow the implementation proposed by Afonso and Jalles [2019]. The impulse response functions (IRFs) are therefore obtained using the following equation:

$$G_{i,t+h}^c - G_{i,t}^c = \beta_S^h \text{Force}_{i,t} + \sum_{j=1}^l \phi_j^h G_{i,t-j}^c + \theta^h E_{i,t-1} + \eta^h P_{i,t} + \alpha_i^h + \gamma_t^h + \epsilon_{i,t}^h \quad (3)$$

Central government expenditure is denoted by G for horizons $h = 1, \dots, 5$ (in years), and is measured in percentage of GDP. The superscript c in G^c denotes the spending category as defined in Table 1, with $c = 0, \dots, 7$.⁶ The variable of interest is the reinforcement of the continuous fiscal rule index in country i in year t , denoted by Force .

Government spending exhibits substantial inertia, as current spending is unlikely to be independent of past decisions. This motivates the inclusion of a lagged dependent variable in the model to capture inertial dynamics.⁷ The vector E includes macroeconomic and more structural control variables lagged by one year to mitigate concerns about reverse causality. These comprise GDP growth and inflation, which capture cyclical and price-level developments affecting expenditure dynamics, the public debt ratio as a proxy for fiscal space and consolidation pressure [Bohn, 1998], as well as age dependency and decentralisation, which account for structural spending needs and cross-country differences in expenditure assignment [Oates, 1972]. The vector P contains political control variables measured in

⁶While the value $c = 0$ is not defined in Table 1, it corresponds to total central government spending.

⁷The number of lags l is set to one, based on the Akaike Information Criterion.

the current year, capturing government support, party system fragmentation and electoral timing, which may affect the capacity and incentives to implement fiscal adjustment [Rogoff and Sibert, 1988]. All variables are described in detail in the Annex A.1.

Preferences for certain spending categories may vary substantially across countries due to structural characteristics, as discussed in the descriptive analysis in Section 3. To address this concern, we include country fixed effects, denoted α_i . In addition, the results may be influenced by shocks that commonly affect countries in the sample, such as the 2007 financial crisis. These common movements are captured by time fixed effects, denoted γ_t . The term $\epsilon_{i,t}$ represents the stochastic error term, to which standard assumptions apply.

The first objective of this paper is to analyse whether a strengthening of fiscal rules leads to a reduction in the level of public spending, and whether such a reduction is evenly distributed across spending categories. Accordingly, Figure 3 plots the cumulative impulse response functions (IRFs) for the different COFOG categories following a shock to fiscal rule stringency, estimated using OLS with heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation-consistent standard errors (Driscoll–Kraay).

The first panel, which depicts the effect of a one-standard-deviation increase in the fiscal rule stringency index (FRSI) on total central government spending, confirms findings from the existing literature (Debrun et al. [2008]; Badinger and Reuter [2017]; Nomo Beyala [2025]). More stringent fiscal rules are found to constrain policymakers’ discretion, albeit with some delay, leading to a reduction in total spending of 0.66 percentage points after three years. This decline remains statistically significant at the end of the five-year horizon considered, cumulating to a reduction of 0.76 percentage points.

The effects of fiscal rule enforcement are nonetheless unevenly distributed across COFOG categories. First, it is noteworthy that general public services (notably including spending on central government executive and legislative bodies) appear largely unaffected by increased rule stringency. This may point to a form of “prince’s privilege,” whereby expenditure cuts fall disproportionately on categories outside the direct interests of the central

Figure 3: Linear effects of fiscal rule reinforcements on COFOG spending categories (OLS). Estimates are obtained using OLS with Driscoll–Kraay standard errors, robust to heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation. Year $t = 0$ corresponds to the year of enforcement. Solid lines (in percentage points) show the responses of public spending to a fiscal rule shock. Shaded orange areas denote 90% confidence intervals.

executive and legislature, potentially shifting the burden to other levels of government, as suggested by [Blöchliger et al. \[2012\]](#). The defence category also appears relatively shielded from rule enforcement.

By contrast, while becoming statistically significant only after five years, the overall adjustment seems to be driven primarily by reductions in welfare spending (−0.42 percentage points after five years), followed by education (−0.12 percentage points after five years). It is worth noting that these results, except for the defence category, closely mirror those of [Castro \[2017\]](#), who studies the effects of fiscal consolidations on different components of public spending. Our focus on fiscal rules complements this literature by shifting attention from episodic consolidation packages to persistent institutional constraints. Unlike consolidation episodes, often triggered by acute fiscal stress, fiscal rules shape fiscal adjustment more continuously over time. In [Section 5.6](#), we further explore whether their effects vary with sovereign borrowing conditions, as rules may become more binding when market financing constraints tighten.

4.2 Incorporating political conditionality

In addition to assessing the effect of fiscal rule enforcement on various spending categories, this paper also aims to provide a plausible explanation for potential heterogeneity in these effects across categories.

To this end, we exploit a smooth transition function (STF) *à la* [Auerbach and Gorodnichenko \[2012\]](#). We view the STF as particularly well suited to the purpose of this paper. Specifically, since we seek to distinguish the effects of fiscal rules on each spending category across two states defined by governments’ salience for the respective category, relying on a simple dummy variable would entail important drawbacks. Compared to a binary indicator, the STF allows for a smooth (or “fuzzy”) separation between states rather than a hard cutoff, which is especially appropriate when political preferences evolve over time and may be measured with noise in party manifestos. This approach also avoids the need to impose

an arbitrary threshold to define high and low preferences. Finally, the STF provides greater stability in the weighting of observations when data points are concentrated around the cutoff. As shown in Figure 2, a zero threshold, natural for a standardised variable, would likely suffer from such instability. The specification of our model therefore becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{i,t+h}^c - G_{i,t}^c = & \beta_S^{h,Opp} V(z^c) \cdot \text{Force}_{i,t} + \beta_S^{h,Sup} (1 - V(z^c)) \cdot \text{Force}_{i,t} + \sum_{j=1}^l \phi_j^h G_{i,t-j}^c + \theta^h E_{i,t-1} \\
& + \eta^h P_{i,t} + \delta^h \bar{Z}_{i,t}^{-c} + \alpha_i^h + \gamma_t^h + \epsilon_{i,t}^h
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Equation 4 augments Equation 3 by decomposing the effects of fiscal rule enforcement into two states using the smooth transition function $V(z^c) = \frac{\exp(-\psi z^c)}{1 + \exp(-\psi z^c)}$ where z^c is the standardised value of the variable ζ^c defined in Equation 2. We set $\psi = 2$, which we consider a reasonable compromise between an overly diffuse transition and a hard cutoff. Following Afonso and Jalles [2019], we also experiment with alternative values of ψ , and our results are not affected.⁸

The differentiated effects of fiscal rule enforcement are captured by β^{Sup} when political preferences in country i are relatively supportive of category c , and by β^{Opp} otherwise. Compared to Equation 3, an additional important element is the inclusion of the control variable \bar{Z}^{-c} , defined as:

$$\bar{Z}_{i,t}^{-c} = \frac{1}{C-1} \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq c}}^C Z_{i,t}^k, \tag{5}$$

In words, this variable captures the average political preference across all spending categories except the category considered in the equation. We view this as an important control because political preferences are measured as shares of manifesto content, greater emphasis on one topic implies a reallocation of relative attention across categories. In

⁸Results are available upon request.

addition, this control helps limit the influence of governments that are broadly pro-spending across all areas, allowing the analysis to focus more clearly on category-specific preferences.

The results, presented in Figure 4, are consistent with the baseline findings in that the same spending categories are primarily affected by fiscal rule enforcement. However, they add an important nuance: reductions in spending occur only when governments in place are relatively less politically supportive of the category concerned. This suggests that the spending cuts induced by more stringent fiscal rules are not only heterogeneous across categories, but also conditional on the political preferences of the parties in power. In this sense, governments generally tend not to reduce spending in policy areas they prioritise.

The results indicate that the spending categories bearing the largest cuts are also those that account for the largest shares of spending on average. In this respect, with the exception of general public services, welfare and education—averaging 20.3% and 8.5% of GDP across the sample, respectively (Table A.2)—are the categories most affected by stringent fiscal rules when governing parties are politically opposed to them. In this politically opposed state (depicted by the orange bands in Figure 4), welfare and education spending are reduced by 1.1% points and 0.2% points, respectively, indicating that these effects are not only statistically significant but also economically meaningful.

5 Robustness checks and debt-cost heterogeneity

5.1 Addressing dynamic panel bias: System GMM

Since Equation 4 includes a lagged dependent variable among the regressors, concerns may arise regarding its correlation with the error term, leading to the well-known Nickell bias (Nickell [1981]), particularly in our $N > T$ setting. To address this issue, we follow Afonso and Jalles [2019] and employ the system-GMM estimator proposed by Blundell and Bond [1998] as a robustness check.

The unconditional system-GMM estimates confirm the main results, showing that fiscal

Figure 4: Non-linear effects of fiscal rule reinforcements on COFOG spending categories (OLS). Green (orange) IRFs indicate the high- (low-) preference state. Estimates are obtained using Driscoll–Kraay standard errors, robust to heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation. Note: $t = 0$ denotes the year of enforcement. Solid lines (in % points) show the responses of public spending to the fiscal rule shock. Shaded green (orange) areas represent 90% confidence bands.

rule enforcement is effective in reducing government spending (Figure A.1). Overall, the conditional results (presented in Figure A.2) remain very similar to those obtained under the OLS specification, with fiscal rule enforcement leading to reductions in several spending categories primarily in the low political-preference scenario.

5.2 Alternative measurement of the dependent variable

Another source of concern relates to the measurement of some variables. In particular, several variables in Equation 4 are expressed as a share of nominal GDP. As a result, cyclical, seasonal, or one-off fluctuations in GDP may induce spurious correlations between the dependent variable and some of the regressors. To mitigate this issue, we follow Kappeler and Väilä [2008] and use trend GDP as the denominator of the dependent variable.⁹ Trend GDP is computed by decomposing GDP into its trend and cyclical components using the Hodrick–Prescott (HP) filter with a smoothing parameter $\lambda = 100$, which is standard for annual data.

The results obtained using this alternative measurement of the dependent variable, reported in Table A.3, confirm the main findings, with the same spending categories being reduced primarily when governments are relatively less politically supportive of them.

5.3 Placebo test with randomised fiscal rule enforcement

In addition to concerns related to measurement and estimation methods, one could argue that the spending reductions observed in the state-dependent scenario are not driven by tighter fiscal rules, but rather by political preferences themselves. A careful reader may counter this argument by noting that similar reductions are observed for total spending and broadly the same categories in the linear specification. Nevertheless, if underlying changes

⁹We note that expressing each spending category as a share of total expenditure could represent an alternative approach to addressing these spurious correlations. However, we prefer using trend GDP as the denominator in order to avoid mechanical increases in the remaining categories, $\sum_{k=1}^C_{k \neq c}$, following a reduction in spending category c .

in political preferences were to systematically coincide with episodes of rule reinforcement, this concern could still persist.

To assess the robustness of our results to this possibility, we implement a falsification (placebo) test by randomly reassigning the fiscal rule stringency values across countries within each year. Under this approach, if political preferences—rather than fiscal rules—were driving the observed effects, one would expect to recover similar results, since swapping a country’s rule stringency with that of another country observed in the same year should have little impact on the estimates.

The results, presented in Figure A.4, show markedly different and largely non-significant effects when using randomly reassigned rules, even though the state-dependence with respect to political preferences is preserved. This finding supports the interpretation that fiscal rule enforcement, rather than political preferences alone, drives the observed spending responses. It therefore dampens the concern raised above and supports interpreting the previous results as conditional effects, rather than spurious correlations between the shock and the state variable.

5.4 Filtering out the populist parties

Another potential source of concern in the analysis relates to the presence of populist parties among governing coalitions. Two main reasons suggest that populist parties may introduce additional noise into the analysis. First, populist parties are often characterised by blurred or internally inconsistent political preferences, as documented by [Zulianello and Larsen \[2024\]](#), which may affect the accuracy of our manifesto-based measure used to define political-preference states. Second, populist incumbencies may be associated with systematic institutional and macroeconomic distortions that complicate the interpretation of the effect of fiscal rules. In particular, [Funke et al. \[2023\]](#) document that populist leaders tend to generate persistent declines in economic performance and institutional quality relative to non-populist counterfactuals.

To address these concerns, we replicate the analysis after excluding populist parties from the sample prior to constructing the political-preference indicator defined in Equation 2. In total, 159 party observations (noting that the same populist party may appear in multiple manifesto years) are removed based on classifications from the PopuList database [Rooduijn et al., 2024]. The results, presented in Figure A.5, show no significant departure from the baseline findings, indicating that our estimates are not materially affected by the inclusion of the relatively small number of populist parties that participated in EU governments over the sample period.

5.5 Using the distance between government and opposition preferences

One final robustness check consists of adopting an alternative measure of the political-preference state variable by exploiting the distance between the preferences of governing parties and those of the opposition. To this end, we slightly modify Equation 2 by subtracting opposition preferences weighted by their parliamentary seat shares, so as to better capture the relevance of the government’s direct competitors:

$$\zeta_{it}^c = \left(\sum_g (\text{Positive}_{git}^c - \text{Negative}_{git}^c) \times \text{SeatShare}_{git} \right) - \left(\sum_o (\text{Positive}_{oit}^c - \text{Negative}_{oit}^c) \times \text{SeatShare}_{oit} \right), \quad (6)$$

where the index g denotes the G parties in government and o the O parties in opposition.

Under this specification, the state variable no longer reflects only the absolute preferences of the parties in power, but rather their preferences relative to those of the opposition. Beyond providing a robustness check using an alternative definition of political preferences, this extension also allows us to explore a more nuanced hypothesis akin to the strategic

setting described in [Alesina and Tabellini \[1990\]](#). In particular, if parliamentary seat shares are interpreted as a proxy for future electoral competition, this measure captures a scenario in which incumbents may seek to tie the hands of potential successors by disproportionately cutting spending in categories that future governments are more likely to prioritise, or to which they are relatively less opposed. While a more targeted empirical design would be required to test this hypothesis conclusively, the results do not allow us to reject it.

The results, presented in [Figure A.6](#), are broadly consistent with the baseline findings, although the magnitude of the estimated effects varies across spending categories. For example, the estimated impact of a more stringent fiscal rule on welfare spending under a politically unfavourable incumbent is larger in absolute terms in the baseline specification (around -1% point after five years) than under the distance-based measure (around -0.75% points after five years). By contrast, the cumulative effect on education spending is slightly stronger in the unfavourable-incumbent scenario when using the distance-to-opposition measure (around -0.25% points after five years), compared with the baseline estimate (around -0.17% points after five years).

5.6 Heterogeneity by sovereign borrowing costs

Finally, one may also question whether the effects of fiscal rule enforcement differ depending on governments' access to debt financing. While more stringent fiscal rules have been shown to reduce spending in categories that incumbent governments tend to prioritise less, this effect may be particularly pronounced when financing constraints are tighter.

As mentioned above, one advantage of the smooth transition approach *à la* [Auerbach and Gorodnichenko \[2012\]](#) is that all observations are retained, with different weights assigned depending on the probability of being in one state or the other. Building on this framework, we conduct an additional heterogeneity analysis by splitting the sample according to the level of interest rates paid on long-term sovereign debt, measured by 10-year

government bond yields.¹⁰

Figure 5 presents the results across two panels. Subfigures 5a–5g display the effects of tighter fiscal rules conditional on political preferences for each spending category in countries characterised by lower average sovereign interest rates over the sample period. In this group, some spending categories do experience reductions following fiscal rule tightening, but these effects arise primarily when incumbent governments are relatively less supportive of the category concerned. A particularly illustrative case is education (Subfigure 5f), where stricter fiscal rules lead to a statistically significant reduction in education spending only in the low-preference scenario, amounting to approximately 0.15% points.

By contrast, the magnitude of the estimated cumulative effects is substantially larger in the high-interest-rate subsample (Subfigures 5h–5n). Using education as a benchmark (Subfigure 5m), a strengthening of fiscal rules results in a reduction of around 0.38% points in education spending after five years when governments exhibit low political support for this category. Similarly, the contraction in welfare spending is largely driven by countries facing higher sovereign borrowing costs, with Subfigure 6n showing a reduction of approximately 1% point after five years.

Overall, these findings indicate that while fiscal rule enforcement in EU countries tends to induce spending cuts primarily in categories that are less favoured by incumbent governments, such adjustments are considerably more pronounced under less favourable sovereign debt conditions, as reflected in higher government bond yields. In that regard, the results are particularly timely given the recent increase in sovereign borrowing costs across EU countries.

¹⁰Long-term government bond yield data used to define the subsamples are drawn from the CPDS (Armingeon et al. [2022]).

Figure 5: Non-linear spending effects of fiscal rule reinforcements on COFOG spending categories (OLS), split by sovereign bond yield levels. Estimates are obtained using Driscoll–Kraay standard errors, robust to heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation. Note: $t = 0$ denotes the year of enforcement. Solid lines (in % points) show the responses of public spending to the fiscal rule shock. Shaded green (orange) areas represent 90% confidence bands.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, leveraging local projections *à la* [Jordà \[2005\]](#) on a sample of EU-27 countries over the period 1995–2019, we first show that stricter fiscal rules are associated with lower total central government spending. We then innovatively match COFOG spending categories with the thematic classifications of the Manifesto Project Database to examine whether spending cuts are disproportionately concentrated in categories that governments favour less, as captured by textual analysis of governing parties’ election manifestos. Relying on a smooth transition framework *à la* [Auerbach and Gorodnichenko \[2012\]](#) to distinguish between high- and low-preference states for each spending category, we find that this hypothesis cannot be rejected.

These findings are subjected to a broad set of robustness checks. Specifically, we vary the estimation method by employing system GMM, replace nominal GDP with trend GDP (constructed using the HP filter) as the denominator of spending variables to mitigate cyclical correlations, conduct a placebo test by randomly reassigning fiscal rule stringency across countries, exclude populist parties to reduce potential noise in manifesto-based preference measures, and test an alternative definition of political preferences based on the distance between government and opposition positions rather than absolute government preferences. While our main results remain robust across this battery of tests, the latter extension also suggests that we cannot reject the interpretation that spending cuts may reflect an attempt by incumbents to tie the hands of future governments, in the spirit of [Alesina and Tabellini \[1990\]](#), albeit operating through spending composition rather than debt accumulation.

Finally, exploiting the fact that smooth transition local projections retain all observations across states, we further explore heterogeneity based on sovereign borrowing conditions by splitting the sample according to countries’ average long-term sovereign bond yields. This additional dimension is motivated by the notion that fiscal rule enforcement may not necessarily entail spending cuts when access to debt markets is favourable, but may instead reinforce fiscal discipline primarily when financing conditions tighten. Our re-

sults indicate that fiscal rule enforcement leads to more pronounced reductions in spending categories that are less favoured by incumbent governments precisely in countries facing higher sovereign borrowing costs. We view this heterogeneity as reinforcing the relevance of our findings in a context marked by rising sovereign bond yields across EU countries.

Further considerations

The results of this paper could have several implications for the design of fiscal frameworks and the role of fiscal institutions in advanced economies. While a large body of the literature has documented that fiscal rules are associated with improved aggregate fiscal outcomes, including lower deficits, reduced debt accumulation, and enhanced fiscal credibility (e.g. [Debrun et al. \[2008\]](#); [Eyraud et al. \[2018\]](#); [Apeti et al. \[2024\]](#)), our findings suggest that fiscal rules also operate through a political economy channel that affects the composition of public expenditure.

This mechanism can be interpreted in two distinct ways. On the one hand, the fact that fiscal rules interact with governments' stated policy priorities, as measured through manifesto data, can be viewed as an expression of democratic accountability. Budgetary adjustments following enforcements of rules reflect electoral mandates and the preferences of governing coalitions, rather than being purely technocratic responses to numerical constraints. In this sense, fiscal rules do not eliminate political choice; instead, they reallocate it within a constrained budget envelope.

On the other hand, this same mechanism raises concerns about the intertemporal consistency of public spending priorities. When governments alternate frequently and hold divergent preferences over spending categories, fiscal rules may amplify policy volatility in expenditure composition. In the presence of political turnover, each incumbent government may strategically compress spending in categories it values less, knowing that future governments with different preferences will face tighter fiscal constraints. This dynamic is closely related to the political economy framework developed by [Alesina and Tabellini](#)

[1990] and subsequent work on strategic debt and policy-making, but applied here to the composition of public spending rather than to debt accumulation itself. In such a context, fiscal rules may inadvertently generate myopic or inconsistent long-term investment patterns, even when aggregate fiscal sustainability is preserved.

These considerations have direct implications for the design of fiscal rules. First, they suggest that numerical rules focusing exclusively on aggregate targets may be insufficient to safeguard long-term policy objectives, particularly for expenditure categories with delayed returns or diffuse political constituencies. This argument resonates with recent calls to move beyond overly simple fiscal rules toward frameworks that better reflect the complexity of fiscal policy-making (e.g. Blanchard et al. [2021]; Arnold et al. [2022]). While the introduction of golden rules or expenditure exemptions has been proposed as a solution, our results indicate that such mechanisms require careful design and strong institutional oversight to prevent strategic reclassification and political manipulation.

A potential succession of governments with different preferences creating inconsistent cuts in the long-run could also advocate for going beyond Medium-Term Fiscal-Structural Plans (MFSPs). Indeed, MFSPs usually coincide with the government cycle duration (usually 4 years extendable to 7 years). While this may limit the concerns of short-term inconsistencies, this step forward compared to the previous SGP may not suffice to trigger some inter-partisan agreements over the structural challenges to be faced over the longer-run (e.g. ageing, climate, ...). In this sense, one could think of complementing MFSPs with indicative rather than constraining Long-Term Strategic Plans that would be updated infrequently (every 5 years instead of annual updates for MFSPs) and that would therefore encourage inter-partisan agreements over the structural priorities.

Second, the findings strengthen the case for complementing fiscal rules with robust fiscal institutions, not only independent fiscal institutions (IFIs), which are part of our fiscal rule strength indicator, but also specific types of IFIs such as parliamentary budget offices (PBOs). A growing literature emphasizes that IFIs enhance transparency, improve forecast

quality, and support compliance with fiscal rules (e.g. [Debrun and Kinda \[2017\]](#)). OECD analyses further stress that PBOs, as parliamentary-based IFIs, can foster parliamentary consensus and improve the quality of budgetary deliberation by providing non-partisan assessments of fiscal trade-offs [[OECD, 2023](#)]. In light of our results, PBOs may represent a key missing link in strengthening the effectiveness of IFIs, complementing their technical monitoring role by increasing transparency around the compositional and intertemporal consequences of fiscal rule enforcement. By making politically selective expenditure adjustments more visible and subject to parliamentary scrutiny, such institutions may help reduce incentives for governments to compress spending in categories they value less and thereby support greater inter-partisan consistency over long-term priorities.

Finally, the heterogeneity of the effects across market conditions suggests that fiscal frameworks should account for differences in fiscal space and financing constraints. When market access is ample, fiscal rules may primarily discipline inefficient spending, whereas under tighter financing conditions they may induce sharper and more politically selective expenditure cuts. This finding supports recent policy discussions advocating for more state-contingent and country-specific fiscal adjustment paths, particularly within supranational fiscal frameworks. While a rigid target on expenditure within each COFOG category may be counterproductive a relatively flexible range monitored by a PBO may be part of these nationally tailored solutions.

More broadly, monitoring these behaviours also requires timely and high-quality data. Thus, the current revision of the COFOG classification coordinated by United Nations Committee of Experts on International Statistical Classifications is welcome and the double tagging of expenditures with secondary objectives that could belong to other functions (such as climate or use for gender budgeting) would allow further analyses of this type to be more accurate and include cross-cutting topics for already existing concerns such as digital transformation.

Overall, the results of this paper suggest that effective fiscal governance requires an

integrated approach in which numerical rules are embedded within strong institutional environments. Such frameworks should preserve fiscal discipline while mitigating politically induced distortions in spending composition and ensuring greater intertemporal coherence of public policy choices.

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Appendix

Figure A.1: Linear spending effects of fiscal rules reinforcements on the various CO-FOG aggregates (System GMM). Note: $t = 0$ is the year of the enforcement. Solid lines (in % points) are the responses of public spending to the shock. Orange areas represent the 90% confidence bands.

Table A.1: Overview of Variables and Data Sources

Variable	Source	Description
Government spending (and COFOG breakdowns)	Eurostat, COFOG	Central government expenditure by COFOG function [General public services; Defence; Public order and safety; Environmental protection; Recreation, culture and religion; Education; Housing and community amenities + Health + Social protection (grouped under welfare state)] expressed in % of GDP.
Fiscal Rule Strength Index (FRSI)	European Commission, DG ECFI	The FRSI is calculated taking into account five criteria on national fiscal rules: (1) legal base, (2) binding character, (3) bodies monitoring compliance and the correction mechanism, (4) correction mechanisms, and (5) resilience to shocks. These criteria are gathered based on a survey among representatives from the 27 EU Member States.
Governing parties' preferences (salience)	The Manifesto Project Database (MPD)	Percentage of quasi-sentences in each manifesto coded into a specific topic (see table 1). For instance, environmental protection refers to the share of quasi-sentences mentioning pro-environment policies. This variable is further modified to constitute the switching variable between the two states (see equation 2).
GDP growth	CPDS, Armingeon et al. [2022]	Growth of real GDP, percent change from previous year.
Government debt	CPDS, Armingeon et al. [2022]	Gross general government debt (financial liabilities) as a percentage of GDP.
Inflation	CPDS, Armingeon et al. [2022]	Growth of harmonised consumer price index (CPI), all items, percent change from previous year; used as a measure for inflation.
Decentralisation	Eurostat, Table 0900	Tax and social contribution receipts for the local government sector (measured in % of GDP).
Government support	CPDS, Armingeon et al. [2022]	Total government support: seat share of all parties in government, weighted by the number of days in office in a given year.
Electoral fractionalisation	CPDS, Armingeon et al. [2022]	Index of electoral fractionalization of the party system according to the formula proposed by Rae [1968] .
Election	MPD, Author's calculations	Following Gootjes et al. [2021] , the election variable is calculated as $M/12$ in an election year and $(12 - M)/12$ in a pre-election year.
Age dependency	CPDS, Armingeon et al. [2022]	(In)dependency ratio captured by the total labour force as a percentage of population aged 15–64 (participation rate).

Table A.2: Summary statistics of variables used in the LP specification

Statistic	N	Min	Max	Mean	St. Dev.
Central government spending (tot)	650	17.600	58.600	30.575	5.832
Central government spending (def)	650	0.200	3.700	1.329	0.572
Central government spending (gen)	650	2.500	23.000	9.693	4.261
Central government spending (env)	645	-0.500	1.700	0.291	0.269
Central government spending (rec)	650	0.100	2.900	0.627	0.244
Central government spending (wel)	644	1.400	20.300	9.338	4.476
Central government spending (ord)	650	0.500	4.300	1.620	0.566
Central government spending (edu)	650	0.000	8.500	3.379	1.416
Saliency for def	675	-1.156	2.964	-0.112	0.713
Saliency for gen	675	-5.007	1.210	-0.156	0.994
Saliency for env	675	-1.498	4.505	-0.091	0.892
Saliency for rec	675	-1.283	3.671	0.248	1.014
Saliency for wel	675	-1.863	3.059	-0.017	0.956
Saliency for ord	675	-1.204	4.041	-0.009	0.896
Saliency for edu	675	-1.716	3.734	0.008	0.855
Fiscal rule strength indicator	675	-0.986	3.069	0.166	1.023
GDP growth	670	-14.804	25.358	2.750	3.448
Government debt	668	6.600	204.980	64.290	36.686
Inflation	658	-4.478	154.935	3.256	7.698
Decentralisation	650	0.300	15.400	3.584	3.575
Government support	670	0.000	81.800	53.373	10.191
Electoral fractionalization	670	0.506	0.925	0.779	0.083
Election	675	0.000	1.000	0.251	0.315
Age dependency	669	57.776	85.654	71.102	5.610

Figure A.2: Non-linear spending effects of fiscal rules reinforcements on the various COFOG aggregates (system GMM); green (orange) IRFs indicate the high (low) preference state. Note: $t = 0$ is the year of the enforcement. Solid lines (in % points) are the responses of public spending to the shock. Green (orange) areas represent the 90% confidence bands.

Figure A.3: Non-linear spending effects of fiscal rules reinforcements on the various COFOG aggregates measured in % of trend GDP (OLS); green (orange) IRFs indicate the high (low) preference state. Driscoll-Kraay Standard Errors, robust to heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation Note: $t = 0$ is the year of the enforcement. Solid lines (in % points) are the responses of public spending to the shock. Green (orange) areas represent the 90% confidence bands.

Figure A.4: Non-linear spending effects of randomly reassigned fiscal rule reinforcements on COFOG spending categories (OLS). Green (orange) IRFs indicate the high- (low-) preference state. Estimates are obtained using Driscoll–Kraay standard errors, robust to heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation. Note: $t = 0$ denotes the year of enforcement. Solid lines (in % points) show the responses of public spending to the shock. Shaded green (orange) areas represent 90% confidence bands.

Figure A.5: Non-linear spending effects of fiscal rules reinforcements on the various COFOG aggregates (OLS) excluding the populist parties; green (orange) IRFs indicate the high (low) preference state. Driscoll-Kraay Standard Errors, robust to heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation Note: $t = 0$ is the year of the enforcement. Solid lines (in % points) are the responses of public spending to the shock. Green (orange) areas represent the 90% confidence bands.

Figure A.6: Non-linear spending effects of fiscal rules reinforcements on the various COFOG aggregates (OLS); green (orange) IRFs indicate the high (low) preference (compared to the opposition) state. Driscoll-Kraay Standard Errors, robust to heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation Note: $t = 0$ is the year of the enforcement. Solid lines (in % points) are the responses of public spending to the shock. Green (orange) areas represent the 90% confidence bands.